

SEED DIVERSITY FAIR BIHAR

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Compiled and submitted By

Vikas Arora

Project Coordinator

Public Advocacy Initiatives for Rights and Values in India (PAIRVI)

Under

FAO (ITPGR) BSF-IV Cycle Project for India on Improving pulse biodiversity in rice fallow areas of tribal belts of Central and East Indian states to bring resilience in the farming practice, provide livelihood support and enhance nutritional level of the tribal population

Background

The FAO funded project on “Improving pulse biodiversity in rice fallow areas of tribal belts of Central and East Indian states to bring resilience in the farming practice, provide livelihood support and enhance nutritional level of the tribal population”. This innovative project is implemented by PAIRVI, New Delhi in five states including Bihar. The aim of the project is to enhance the availability and onfarm conservation of resilient varieties of pulses (traditional varieties, varieties procured from gene banks as well as under-utilized species of pulses) and oil seeds for cultivation during the rice fallow season. The project decided to conduct community seeds fair on 18th December 2022 at its project location, Chakai block, Jamui district under Bihar State.

Strategies

Bihar team of PAIRVI prepared the following strategies for conducting the one day “Community Seed Fair” successfully.

1. Effective implementation designed for achieving the effective and meaningful seed fair
 - a. Farming community and volunteers at project location played a key role. The project volunteers and farming community members were oriented on how to mobilize the farmers including women during this challenging time of COVID19.
 - b. A dedicated team / Seed Fair Committee (SFC) consists of community members led by State Coordinator, conducted the fair.
 - c. Team concentrated to the project villages and adjacent area of the project location only. The local officials from Panchayat Raj Institutions (PRIs) and agriculture department also were invited.
 - d. Planned to build low-cost stalls, main entrance gate and stage for cultural events (tents / pandal) to attract the tribal and other participants.
 - e. Display of IEC materials for creating awareness on diversified pulse cultivation and COVID19 among the farmers.
 - f. The responsible persons of team were taking care of registration, photography/ video, foods, logistics, sanitization, reporting etc.
2. The rejuvenate project team to achieving the following targeta. Permission from administration:
 - b. Selection of fair location: Open ground of Ghatiyani field
 - c. Purchasing of clay pots: For display
 - d. Finalization of farmers for display at stalls: Both men and women
 - e. Selection of Vendors / suppliers: Especially for food and tents/pandal
 - f. Door to door visit: At least 100 farming families
 - g. Awareness and miking: 5 project habitations and adjacent village
 - h. Invitation to local officials: At least 10 members including Govt.
 - i. Follow up action plan for implementation: Emerged from CSF
3. It is mandatory to follow the guideline of the government regarding COVID-19 during the Community Seed Fair (CSF)
 - a. Maintaining social distancing during community mobilization and CSF.
 - b. Wearing musk is must by the farmers/participants, volunteers, coordinator, officials etc. Planned to provide mask and sanitizers to all participants.
 - c. There will not be more than 5 persons in the queue or any other discussion / gathering

or food serving. Volunteers will maintain all these.

d. All participants will wash their hands thoroughly with soap-water and sanitizer and enter the ground of fair campus. Volunteers will pour sanitizer into their hands in front of main entrance and monitor the whole process.

e. Will display the slogan as a part of IEC (Information, education and communication) materials to fight against COVI19.

4. State coordinator invited the the higher official of agriculture department, farm manager, scientist from Agriculture University and KVK, PRI members etc. for ensuring their participation in the fair.

5. The project team prepared a list of participants with their signature for reporting purpose.

Committees and Participation:

There were around 40 farmers including 25 women from project location and adjacent villages. The following table shows the active participation community leaders to make the community fair successful.

Sl.	Activities (Number of responsible persons)	Name of the committee-members	Contact Number
1.	Registration (2)	Sukurmuni marandi	7061194773
		Anita murmu	"
2.	Logistic team (4)	Biku ram	8809534560
		Paltan ram	8294953876
		Bablu soren	"
		Parwati marandi	"
3.	Decoration committee (3)	Jitendra prabhakar	9199877879
		Vijay yadav	"
		Mukun kumar	"
4.	Cultural committee (10)	Anita murmur	8539840868
		Muni devi	7739712639
		Nirmala murmur	
		Saloni marandi	7294872214
		Mamta hembrom	"
		Barki murmur	"
		Sukurmuni marandi	"
		Sangita soren	"
		Soni tudu	"
Gita kisku	"		
5	Stall response video (1)	Sudhansu kumar	9031934146
6	Stall response from fill-up	Upendra kumar	6206460006
5.	Face book live (2)	Rajrsh kumar	
6.	Exit interview video (1)	Lakhsman kumar	9199996833
7.	Media / news paper publication (2)	R. k.jha	"
8.	Overall monitoring (1)	Subhash chand dube	
9.	Overall supervision (1)	Primal kumar singh	9852455918

SEED FAIR: IMAGES/Photographs:

Scientist Parimal Kumar ji visited the stall

Youth and students on farmer's stall in seed fair

Fair Outcomes and Impacts:

The following shows the immediate outcome of this event

- There were 30 stalls presented by the farmers and displayed diversified local seeds including mustard, sunflower, black gram, lentil, paddy, til/niger, elephant foot yam, turmeric etc. Some of the farmers also exchange their seeds
- There were more than 40 farmers participated in the fair and they realized the important of seeds and benefits of pulse cultivation as well. Some of the farmers (limited number) also purchased the seeds.
- The official from agriculture department and members of local governance also participated in the fair. This fair built the relationship among the project team, farming community and service providers.
- The self-efficacy among the farmers increased toward pulse cultivation by using traditional and scientific knowledge.

Seed Diversity in Fair 2022:

s.l.	Diversified seeds	Number of varieties	Stalls No (best stall)
1	Urad	1	01 and 30
2	Mustard (black)	3	
3	Masoor	2	
4	Til / Niger	0	
5	Mustard yelloe	2	
6	Tishi	1	
7	Khesari	0	
8	Arhar	1	
9	Maize	3	
10	Paddy	3	
11	Peas	0	

12	Lotni	1	
13	Ragi	2	
14	White til	1	
15	Black til	1	
16	Kudrum red	1	
17	Kudrum	1	
18	Moong	2	
19	Ghaghra	1	
20	Bazra/Maize	1	
21	Sonai	1	
22	bhelwa	1	
		Total =29 verity	

Seed Distribution in fair

- Almost **35 farmers received different kinds of seeds (½ kg to 1kg) from the project.** The farmers and other stakeholders appreciated this initiative.

Women participation

- There were more than 130 farmers participated including **63 women farmers** in the fair and they realized the important of seeds and benefits of pulse cultivation as well.

Stakeholders

- The officials and delegates from govt. department, (KVK) Krishi Vigyan Kendra). This fair built the relationship among the project team, farming community and service providers. The following table shows the involvement of different stakeholders in the community seeds fair towards promotion of pulse and seeds.

S.No.	Name of the stakeholders	Address
1	Primal kumar singh	KVK (deoghar)
2	Lalmohan prsad yadav	Ex Mukhiya
3	Subhashchandra dubey	L.V.S (JAMUI)
4	Budhan marandi	Ward Member
5	Bablu sore	Village, Pradhan (chihra)
6	Raji ranjan sinng	Deoghar

5.5 Awarded two stalls for biodiversity

- Two best stalls are awarded (Rs. 500/- each) by the project due to diversified seeds displayed and good gathering of farmers. **Stall No 01 And 30.**

5.6 Awarded women in cultural programme

- There were games and cultural events for the participants to mobilize the farming community. Ten (10) women were awarded (Rs. 200/- each) for active participation in the cultural events. **The following table shows the list of those women.**

s.no.	Name	Phone	Award amount
1	Nilmoni marandi	"	200
2	Logni marandi	9905511850	200
3	Barki soren	6207389554	200

4	Subodi soren	8083590455	200
5	Makul hembrem	"	200
6	Aasha murmur	7858089617	200
7	Rani murmur	"	200
8	Phulmuni soren	"	200
9	Rina soren	6299871464	200
10	Sarita hembrom	9955096922	200
11	Sunita soren	"	200

6. Way forward

- Linkage and convergence created through community seeds fair. The farmers are quite empowered towards pulse cultivation and farmers are planning to cultivate pulses and oil seeds in this winter.
- This seeds fair provided opportunity to the project team to scaling out the pulse, millets and oilseeds cultivation in rice fallow area of different district.

Stalls in Seed Fair 2022

SEED DIVERSITY IN FAIR 2022

Stall No, Name of Farmers with Address	Crop/Seed displayed	Main crop, Millets, Pulses, Vegetables, Oil	Varieties /Local name	Local (L) / Improved (I)	Major, Neglected, Rare, Wild
Stall No 30 Name: Shanti Soren vill,ghatiyani bihar	Maize	Millts	Disi	L	Major
	Tisi	Oil	“	L	Neglected
	Kulthi	Pulses	“	L	Neglected
	Chana	Pulses	“	L	Neglected
	Urad	Pulses	“	L	Neglected
	Masoor	Pulses	“	L	Neglected
	kudrum	oil	“	L	neglected
Stall No 29 Name: Bablu Kumar Soren Vill. Chihara Bihar	paddy	Main crop	sorna	I	major
	maize	milletts	Rad maize	L	major
	kudrum	oil	Red kudrum	L	major
	masur	pulses	dehi	L	neglected
	musted	oil	Black musted	L	neglected
	chana	pulses	Chota chana	L	neglected
	urad	pulses	Black urad	L	neglected
Stall No 28 Name: Shila Kumari Vill. Nawadih, Bihar	paddy	Main crops	775	H	major
	maize	milletts	deshi	L	major
	teshe	oil	deshi	L	neglected
	kulthi	pulses	deshi	L	major
	masoor	pulses	market	I	neglected
Stall No 27 Name: Sangita soren Vill. Khelkola bihar	paddy	Main crops	Saktiman lalath	I	major
	urad	pulses	urad	hart	neglected
	moong	pulses	mung	L	pulses
	maize	milletts	Red maize	L	major
	jowar	milletts	jawar	L	neglected
	arhar	pulses	Disi arhar	L	major
	chana	pulses	chana	L	neglected
Stall No 26 Name: Sunita devi Vill: Basahra bihar	paddy	Main crops	Sulfa lalath	I	
	maize	milletts	disi	L	
	Yellow musted	oil	market	H	
	Tesi	oil	disi	L	
	Kudrum black	Oil	disi	L	
	Ragi	milletts	disi	L	

Stall No. 25 Name: Kusum hembrem Vill: Parsatade bihar	paddy	Main crops	Tiger	I	major
	mung	pulses	disi	L	major
	ghangra	pulses	disi	L	neglected
	tesi	oil	disi	L	neglected
	maize	milletts	disi	L	major
	kasawa	milletts	disi	L	neglected
Stall no,24 name rina biske vill parsatade	paddy	Main crops	Mahan sorna	I	Major
	maize	milletts	kanchan	H	Major
	tesi	oil	disi	L	neglected
	kudrum	oil	disi	L	neglected
	chana	pulses	disi	L	neglected
Stall No 23 Name: Kiran kumara Vill. : Chihra bihar	maize	milletts	White maize	L	Major
	moong	pulses	disi	L	Major
	musted	Oil	disi	L	neglected
	Yellow musted	Oil	disi	L	neglected
	Lotni	Oil	disi	L	neglected
	chana	pulses	disi	L	neglected
	paddy	Main crops	Habred	775 habred	Main crops
Stall No 22 Name: Badki soren Vill: Parsatade	Paddy	Main crops	Tiger	I	major
	Maize	milletts	kanchan	H	major
	Recha black	Oil	disi	L	neglected
	Lotni	oil	disi	L	neglected
	Ragi	milletts	disi	L	neglected
	Kudrum white	oil	disi	L	neglected
Stall no 21 Name: Munne devi Vill- Padhpur bihar	Paddy	Main crops	2281	H	Major
	wheat	Main crops	disi	L	Major
	Rice	rice	Sorna	I	Major
	tesi	oil	disi	L	Major
	maize	milletts	disi	L	Major
	Bajra	milletts	disi	L	neglected

Stall no 20 Name anita marande Vill sirsiya	Paddy	Main crops	Mahan,sorna	I	Major
	Rice	Main crops	lalath	I	Major
	kudrum	Oil	disi	L	neglected
	papaya	frute	disi	L	neglected
	pallak	vegetable	disi	L	major
	maize	maiets	disi	L	major
	shim	vegitable	disi	L	major
Stall No 19 Name: hareram yadav, Vill: bashara	Paddy	Main crops	lalath	I	Major
	Maize	milletts	disi	L	Major
	Chana	pulses	disi	L	neglected
	Kulthi	pulses	disi	L	Major
	Urad	pulses	market	I	neglected
	Musted black	Oil	market	I	Major
	Yellow musted	Oil	disi	L	neglected
Stall no 18 name sandip singh vill Ghtinyani bihar	Paddy	Main crops	6444	H	Major
	Maize	milletts	disi	L	Major
	Til black	Oil	disi	L	Major
	Tesi	Oil	disi	L	Neglected
	Kulthi	Pulses	disi	L	Major
Stall no 17 Name chotki hasda vill kherkola	Paddy	Main crops	Sorna 1	I	Major
	Moong	Pulses	Maeket	I	Major
	Maize	Milletts	Disi red	L	Major
	Chana	Pulses	Market	I	Neglected
	Masoor	Pulses	Disi	L	Neglected
	Kulthi	Pulses	Disi	L	Neglected
	Urad	Pulses	Market	I	Neglected
Stall no16 Name sumri marandi Vill: Chihra	Paddy	Main crops	Sorna	i	Major
	Moong	Pulses	Lokal	L	Major
	Red kudrum	Oil	L	L	Neglected
	Til black	Oil	L	L	Major
	Masoor	Pulses	L	L	Neglected
	Kudrum	Oil	L	L	Neglected
	Ragi	Milletts	L	L	Neglected
Stall no 15 name santi marandi vill kherkola	Maize	Milletts	L	L	Major
	Arahar	Pulses	L	L	Major
	Kulthi	Pulses	L	L	Major
	Chana	Pulses	L	L	Neglected

	Paddy 775	Main crops	Habred 775	habred	Major
	Yellow musted	Oil	L	L	Neglected
	Urad	Pulses	L	L	Neglected
Stall no 14 name manjhli hasda vill kherkola	Black musted	Oil	L	L	Neglected
	Ragi	Millet s	L	L	Neglected
	bearly	Main crops	bearly	L	Neglected
	Kulthi	Pulses	L	L	Major
	Paddy sorna	Main crops	Sorna	I	Major
	Masoor	Pulses	L	L	Neglected
Stall no 13 name sonmuni hambrem vill chihra bihar	Moong	Pulses	L	L	Major
	Maize	Millets	Red	L	Major
	Kudrum	Oil	Red	L	Neglected
	Til	Oil	Black	L	Major
	Ghaghra	Pulses	Lokal	L	Major
	Urad	Pulses	Local	L	Neglected
	Chana	Pulses	L	L	Neglected
Stall no 12 name jirmila murmur vill paharpur	Kudrum	Oil	L	L	Neglected
	Urad	Pulses	L	L	Neglected
	Ragi	Millets	L	L	Neglected
	Masoor	Pulses	L	L	Major
	Black musted	Oil	L	L	Major

	arhar	Pulses	L	L	Major
	Paddy	Main crops	Sorna	I	Major
Stall no 11 name dholiya murmu vill chihara	Yellow musted	Oil	Arun	I	Neglected
	Moong	Pulses	L	L	Major
	Kudrum	Oil	L	L	Neglected
	Maize	Millets	L white	L	Major
	Ghaghra	Pulses	L	L	Major
	Jawar	Millets	L	L	Neglected
	Tesi	Pulses	L	L	Neglected
Stall no 10 name ,barki murmur ,paharpur	Paddy	Main crop	Lalat	I	Major
	Kulthi white	Pulses	L	L	Major
	Arhar	Pulses	L	L	Major
	Chana	Pulses	Pusa	I	Neglected
	Til	Oil	L	L	Major
	Urad	pulses	L	L	Neglected
Stall no 9,name ,mamata hembrom,paharpur	Black musted	Oil	L	L	Major
	Kulthi	Pulses	L	L	Major
	Maize	millits	L	L	Major
	Bazra	Millets	L	L	Neglected
	Kulthi white	Pulses	L	L	Major

	Ragi	Millets	L	L	neglected
	moong	Pulses	L	L	major
Stall no 8,name muni devi vill,paharpur	Kulthi	Pulses	L	L	Major
	Tisi	Oil	L	L	Neglected
	bearly	Main crop	L	L	Neglected
	Arahar	Pulses	L	L	Major
	Rice	Main crop	L	L	Major
	Ghaghra	Pulses	L	L	Major
	Paddy	Main crop	sorna	i	Major
Stall no 7,name ,saloni marandi ,vill,paharpur	Urad	Pulses	L	L	Neglected
	Bazra	Millets	L	L	Neglected
	Chana	Pulses	L	L	Neglected
	Yellow musted	Oil	L	L	Major
	Arhar	Pulses	L	L	Major
	moong	Pulsesl	L	L	major
Stall no 6 name bahamuni marandi vill,chira	Moong	Pulses	L	L	Major
	Maize	Millets	L	L	Major

	Paddy	Main crop	Lalat	L	Major
	Ladyfinger	Vegitables	Vegitables	L	Neglected
	Loki	Vegitables	Vegitable	L	neglected
	Ghaghra	Pulses	L	L	Major
	ragi	miltes	L	L	neglected
Stall no 5,name,barki marandi, vill,kherkola	Paddy	Main crop	Lalat	I	Major
	Maize	Millets	L	L	Major
	Bearly	Other	L	L	Neglect
	Masoor	Pulses	L	L	Neglected
	Maize desi	Millets	L	L	Major
	Tisi	Oil	L	L	Neglected
	urad	pulses	L	L	neglected
Stall no 4 name vill,chiara	Moong	Pulses	L	L	Neglected
	Paddy	Main crop	Sorna	L	Main crop
	Chana	Pulses	Ll	L	Neglected
	Til	Oil	L	L	Major
	Ghaghra	Pulses	L	L	Major
	kulthi	pulses	L	L	major
	urad	pulses	l	l	neglected
Stall no 3 name ,soni tudu,vill,kherkola	Moong	Pulses	L	L	Major
	Paddy	Main crop	Lalat	I	Major
	Chana	Puses	L	L	Neglected
	Moong	Pulses	L	L	Major

	Ghaghra	Pulses	L	L	Neglected
	Urad	Pulses	L	L	Neglected
	kudrum	Oil	L	L	neglected
Stall no 2 name ,vill,kherkola	Paddy	Main crop	lalal	I	Major
	Moong	Pulses	L	L	Major
	Musted yellow	Oil	L	L	Major
	Chana	Puses	L	L	Neglected
	Urad	Pulses	L	L	Neglected
	Kudrum	Oil	L	L	Neglectd
	Kulthi	pulses	L	L	neglected
Stall no 01, name .anita murmur,vill,paharpur	Maize	Mailts	L	L	Major
	Ragi	Mailts	L	L	Neglected
	Paddy		Saktimam	I	Major
	Moong	pulses	L	L	Major
	Ghaghra	pulses	L	L	Neglected
	Rice	Main crop	L	L	Major
	Black musted	oil	L	L	Neglected
	Karencch	Aushadhi,leaf	L	L	Neglected
	Tulsi	“	L	L	Major
	Bhelwa	“	L	L	Neglected
	Sinei	“	L	L	Neglected
	Ber	“	L	L	Neglected
	Sirwar	“	L	L	Major

	Black maize	millets	L	L	Neglected
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